

Li2BC: From Visible Light Communication to Ambient RF Backscatter

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Abstract—Ambient backscatter communication (AmBC) is a key enabler for the energy-efficient Internet of Things (IoT) that employs existing radio frequency (RF) signals for low-power communication. One open question is how to efficiently send data to the backscatter device (BD) for controlling its operations. Recent research reveals that the ubiquitous presence of configurable light-emitting diodes (LEDs) can leverage such control functionalities by involving visible light communication (VLC). However, existing works only consider relaying the received VLC signals for BD control without storage and processing, which sacrifices configurability and flexibility. In this paper, we propose the Li2BC, a backscatter device (BD) that integrates the VLC receiving, processing, and backscatter modulation functionality. By leveraging a low-power microcontroller, the BD can receive, amplify, demodulate, and store/cache VLC signals. The stored/cached signals are then used for backscatter control. We demonstrate the end-to-end data transmission from LEDs to an RF receiver. The investigations verify that the Li2BC can efficiently receive VLC signals and then use them to control backscatter modulation.

Index Terms—backscatter communication, visible light communication, backscatter device, Internet of Things (IoT).

I. INTRODUCTION

Ambient backscatter communication (AmBC) is emerging as an essential technology for the energy-efficient Internet of Things (IoT) in the beyond 5G era [1]. By enabling low-power and low-cost data exchange, AmBC addresses the energy and complexity constraints of traditional IoT systems. In this scenario, backscatter devices (BDs) operate by modulating and reflecting ambient radio frequency (RF) signals, such as WiFi and cellular signals, eliminating the need for power-hungry transceivers [2]. However, efficiently transmitting control data and supplying energy to BDs remains a challenge for achieving adaptable operation of these systems.

In battery-free AmBC, BDs can be powered by harvesting energy from ambient radios [3]. However, this is often a challenging task due to path losses that RF signals experience. Hence, employing visible light as both an energy source and a control medium is gaining traction in the development of low-power AmBC systems. In [4], the authors demonstrated the potential of light-powered BDs for asset tracking. Similarly, authors in [5] presented a solar-powered backscatter sensor for plant water stress monitoring, and [6] explored a battery-free visible light sensing system powered by solar cells. These works underline the effectiveness of light harvesting for powering BD circuitry yet rely on conventional methods to

control backscatter modulation, such as wiring or transmission lines, which limits the flexibility of the BD control.

Recent research has pushed the boundaries by integrating visible light communication (VLC), not only for energy harvesting but also for backscatter modulation control. For instance, authors in [7], [8] proposed systems where intensity-modulated light is simultaneously used to supply energy and control backscatter operations without requiring a microcontroller (MCU). This approach enhances system simplicity and energy efficiency. However, such passive systems primarily focus on relaying VLC signals for control purposes, lacking the ability to process or store received VLC signals, which limits their configurability to dynamic IoT scenarios.

To address the limitations of existing solutions, we present the Li2BC, a novel backscatter device that integrates VLC receiving, processing, and backscatter modulation functionalities. By utilizing a low-power microcontroller, the Li2BC can receive, amplify, demodulate, and store/cache VLC signals. This caching capability enables the device to store VLC data for subsequent control of backscatter operations, enhancing its configurability and flexibility. Unlike passive devices that simply relay incoming VLC signals, the Li2BC empowers more sophisticated applications by combining light-based communication with signal processing and storage functionalities, paving the way for innovative IoT solutions.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Fig. 1. System model.

Fig. 1 shows an overview of the proposed backscatter communication system enabled by the Li2BC. The LEDs are driven by a constant current LED driver controlled by a pulse-width modulation (PWM) signal. Information can be coded into the frequency of the PWM signal. As long as the frequency of the PWM is above 2 kHz [9], the information encoding does not cause visible flickering of the light. The

Fig. 2. Hardware structure of the Li2BC.

Fig. 3. Implemented prototype with a USB serial port interface for debugging. The serial port interface also powered the prototype for the tests.

duty cycle of the PWM signal affects the LED light intensity, and it must be held constant to avoid any flickering.

The Li2BC is powered by a photovoltaic (PV) cell, which is also used to receive control data over light. As the information is encoded in a high-frequency component, it can be extracted by filtering. The filtered signal is then amplified and fed into the MCU for backscatter control. Internal capacitance and resistance of the PV cell form a circuitry resembling an LPF. This sets an upper limit for the frequency of the light intensity encoding. Depending on the cell used this limit is in 10 kHz to 20 kHz range.

The MCU communicates with BD-embedded sensors, acquiring sensing data periodically. To transmit the data with AmBC, Li2BC uses one of the MCU's timers to generate frequencies for binary frequency shift keying (BFSK) modulation. The MCU changes the timer parameters for every transmitted symbol. The timer can run independently, the rest of the MCU is kept in a low-power state during symbols to conserve energy. The modulated signal controls an RF switch to change an antenna's reflection coefficient backscattering ambient signal. The backscattered signal can be received by commonly used RF receivers.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

The prototype of Li2BC device consists of three main parts implemented in different printed circuit boards (PCBs), with structure presented in Fig. 2. These parts are the VLC receiver, the MCU board and the backscatter radio front end.

The VLC receiver is constructed as an add-on board on top of the MCU board. In the VLC receiver, the signal captured by the PV cell is bandpass filtered and amplified. The amplifier utilizes Texas Instruments TLC2262 dual operational amplifier

Fig. 4. Low-power backscatter communication flow.

(op-amp) [10]. The op-amp is configured as a trans-impedance amplifier followed by a conventional voltage amplifier. The total amplification is 100 kV/A. The bandpass filter (BPF) turns the BFSK signal into on-off-keying (OOK). A schottky diode and a lowpass filter (LPF) detect the received signal envelope. Another LPF is used to measure the mean signal level.

The MCU board is based on an ultra-low-power STM32L562 [11] microcontroller from STMicroelectronics. The MCU includes comparator (COMP), timer (TIMER), and universal asynchronous receiver-transmitter (UART) that can remain operational even if the rest of the MCU is in an energy-saving sleep state. The comparator converts the mean and the envelope signals to logic-level signal. The logic-level signal is fed to the UART, which can wake the MCU for processing. The MCU board also hosts ADP5091 [12] energy harvester, which collects energy from the PV cell, and regulates all of the board voltages. Board also contains four 0.1 F supercapacitors for energy storage. The PCB is the size of a credit card (53 mm \times 85 mm).

When the MCU is in the low-power state, a 32.768 kHz clock is available for the peripherals. This sets the upper limit for the output frequency of the timers to 16.384 kHz. The UART communication speed is up to 9600 baud/s. The clock is generated from a crystal oscillator with 20 ppm frequency tolerance. This also sets the frequency tolerance of the generated frequencies.

The radio front end consists of an Analog Devices single pole RF switch ADG919 [13] connected to a SMA connector. Fig. 4 presents the software flow for the backscatter communication. The control signal for the switch is from an MCU timer, configured to output a square wave with 50% duty cycle.

Fig. 5. Measured and theoretical BER at different SNR levels of the VLC link.

The frequency of the wave is changed based on the bit to be transmitted. Another timer is used to generate an interrupt at the interval of one symbol duration. The interrupt routine of the MCU updates the parameters of the first timer based on the transmitted symbol. Since the timers operate independently, the MCU can remain in a sleep state during the symbols to conserve power.

A configurable light source was implemented as the VLC transmitter. The light source consists of an FPGA board, a LED driver with PWM control and an LED board. To control the light, an NEORV32 [14] MCU and BFSK modulator is implemented on the FPGA board. The UART of the MCU is directly connected to the BFSK modulator within the FPGA. Output of the BFSK modulator is used to control the PWM function of the LED driver.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND EVALUATION

A. VLC link Bit-Error Rate

VLC link bit-error performance of the Li2BC was tested with a 3 W LED light source. The light source was BFSK-modulated with $f_{L1} = 10$ kHz and $f_{L2} = 40$ kHz. The frequencies are high enough so that they do not produce perceptible flicker. In addition, the higher frequency will be attenuated by the lowpass filtering behaviour of the PV cell. Because of the BFSK modulation, the duty cycle of the light was configured to 50%. The measured intensity of the light at the distance of 1 m was 150 lx. To simplify the measurement setup, the Li2BC was powered via the USB serial port interface instead of harvested energy in this test.

Distance between the light source and the Li2BC was varied in 0.9 m to 1.6 m range with 0.1 m steps. 10 000 bytes of random data was transmitted at 9600 baud/s for each measurement. The bit error rate (BER) was calculated from the received data. At distances below 0.9 m no bit errors were detected, and with distances over 1.6 m the received signal amplitude dropped below the detection level. At each distance, the Li2BC signal detector output was captured with

Fig. 6. End-to-end communication system demonstration.

Fig. 7. LED control signal (Channel 1, yellow) and Li2BC received signal (Channel 2, blue).

an oscilloscope and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) was estimated with MATLAB's `snr()` function.

A new byte was transmitted as soon as the Li2BC had acknowledged the reception of a byte. The realized transfer rate over the VLC link was 500 bit/s. Fig. 5 shows the measured BER compared to BFSK theoretical performance $BER = \frac{1}{2} \exp\left(\frac{-SNR}{2}\right)$ [15]. It can be seen that this receiver requires approximately 10 dB higher SNR than optimal BFSK receiver to achieve the same bit error rate. Additionally, the diode detector is not very sensitive, requiring signal amplitude to be over 0.2 V for reliable operation. However, the range of the VLC link is highly dependent on multiple parameters, notably, the PV cell used as the receiver, the intensity of the modulated light source, and the gain of the receiver amplifier. Further research is needed to characterize their effects, and optimize their operation.

B. End-to-End Transmission

An end-to-end data transmission was demonstrated with a test setup shown in Fig. 6. In the test, a PC transmitted random bytes over a serial interface to the LED driver, which modulated the LEDs with BFSK signals where $f_{L1} = 10$ kHz and $f_{L2} = 40$ kHz. The Li2BC received the light and then demodulated it. Fig. 7 shows the LED control signal (channel-1, yellow) and signal received by the Li2BC after bandpass filtering and amplification (channel-2, blue).

Receiving data over the VLC triggered the MCU of the Li2BC to relay sensing data using AmBC. For synchronization and bookkeeping, the sensing data was prefixed with a 7-bit Barker code repeated three times and a 16-bit packet counter. Another BFSK modulation was used to modulate the sensing data with $f_{B1} = 191$ Hz and $f_{B2} = 500$ Hz, with a symbol

Fig. 8. Backscattered signal spectrum from the RF receiver.

length of 40 ms. The resulting signal was then utilized to modulate the incident RF carrier.

An RF signal generator SMBV100A generated the continuous carrier at 433 MHz with an output power of 0 dBm, performing as the ambient RF source. The modulated carrier was backscattered and was received by a spectrum analyzer SSA3075XR, shown in Fig. 8. The signal trace was maximum-held for visualizing the sub-carrier components around the carrier frequency f_c at the frequencies $f_c \pm f_{B1}$ and $f_c \pm f_{B2}$, respectively, which contained the sensing data. The measurements show that the BD can be controlled through the VLC link over a distance of 1 m. As a result, the RF receiver can receive the backscattered signal, where the embedded sensing data is successfully demodulated and recovered.

C. Power Consumption

One goal of the Li2BC implementation was low power consumption. The aim was to be able to operate on harvested energy without any external sources. This was accomplished for the MCU and radio front end parts. The average power consumption of the MCU board in the idle state was 11 μ W. When transmitting over the backscatter link, the power consumption was 27 μ W, including the radio front end. The VLC receiver has a rather high consumption of 3 mW.

During tests, the receiver prototype consumes more energy than is available from the harvester. The high power consumption is mostly due to the amplifier. Amplifiers with similar performance but with lower power consumption are available. However, the power consumption may still be prohibitively high for constant VLC receiver operation. In this case, an operation mode where the receiver is powered only periodically could be implemented. This then requires some level of cooperation with the transmitter. Another weakness of the VLC receiver is the low sensitivity of the detector. This limits the maximum distance over which the VLC link can operate.

V. CONCLUSION AND FURTHER RESEARCH

In this paper, we proposed the Li2BC, a backscatter device that integrates the VLC receiving, processing, and backscatter modulation functionality. By leveraging an MCU combining low power consumption with high performance, the Li2BC can receive, amplify, demodulate, and store/cache VLC signals.

The stored/cached signals are then used for backscatter control. We demonstrated the end-to-end data transmission from LEDs to an RF receiver. The investigation verified that the Li2BC can efficiently receive VLC signals and then use them to control backscatter operations. We also investigated and demonstrated the utility of the integrated, low-power peripherals available in modern microcontrollers for realizing communication links.

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